

Hands-on practices for enhancing researcher mental health and well-being

Occupational health services provided in high education institutions.

A mapping study in Switzerland

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Purpose

Switzerland has 12 recognized public universities: ten cantonal universities and two Federal Institutes of Technology (EPFL and ETHZ). Besides, there are nine universities of applied sciences, which primarily conduct application-oriented research, 20 universities of teacher education, and other high education institutions (HEI) like the Graduate Institute of International and Development Studies in Geneva and the Distance Learning University in Brig. There are also private schools throughout the country and four public research institutes: the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI), the Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research (WSL), the Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology (EMPA) and the Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology (EAWAG).

Swiss universities hold a privileged position among the world's top 200 universities and count about 313,000 students. However, little is known regarding students and researchers' working and health conditions and on how the Swiss HEIs protect and promote their mental health. Within the project ReMeHealP (Researchers' Mental Health Promotion), we launched a mapping study to assess what occupational health services (OHS) are provided in Swiss academia.

Design

We constructed a sample of 14 Swiss HEIs including all HEIs of Lausanne (University of Lausanne, EPFL, Unisante), cantonal universities of Berne, Basel, Geneve, Neuchatel, Fribourg, Lucerne, Lugano, St. Gallen and Zurich, the ETHZ, and the PSI. With this selection we cover all geographic regions and different types of HEI in terms of size, seniority, and scientific orientation.

To identify available OHS, we reviewed the institutional websites and interviewed representatives of the provided OHS. For each HEI we documented the following information: name of services; their aim and type of help provided; personnel involved; access details (e.g.,

how to arrange an appointment, location, opening hours, prices, and usage/application/registration conditions).

Results

We identified a wide variety of OHS provided in Swiss academia. Each HEI has a different approach of OHS, however, at most HEIs it is possible to find help such as access to general or occupational physician, psychological counselling/advisory, and legal advice counselling. A few HEIs offer additional services like coaching sessions, spiritual/religion consultation, sleep consultation points, “Psyline” (i.e., a free telephone advice and psychological support) and workshops on psychological topics. Approximately 90 % of the reviewed HEIs offer psychological support for researchers. This primarily consists of psychological consultations/supporting advice (usually in one or a limited number of sessions), but neither a diagnosis, not regular psychotherapy. For the latter, a referral to an outside professional center can be provided. During the psychological consultations, the session content is protected, and maximum confidentiality is guaranteed, ensuring that each dossier is managed anonymously. The information on how to access OHS is usually well communicated, with a clear and simple instructions on how to arrange an appointment. This information is provided on the HEI’s website and communicated additionally in other social media and university leaflets. The appointments can be made in advance, by email or phone-call, using online platform or personally by ‘passing by in the OH office’. Nearly 70% of HEIs offer OHS within the institution. In the other HEIs, the OHS are ensured by an external specialized institutions in the area (e.g., Center for Psychological Support or Psychotherapy).

The review of available OHS revealed that there are more services provided for students (bachelor, master, PhD level) than for researcher staff. The services for students are also better announced and promoted, while information on more general OHS is less visible. An important difference across HEIs was observed between medical and especially psychological services in terms of prices. Some HEIs provide fully free consultations (e.g., coverage by health insurance or university), while others offer only the first consultation for free, and the following consultations should be either covered by the health insurance or remain at researcher’s charge. A few HEIs charge a certain (although relatively low) fee from the 1st consultation.

Implications

These first results confirm that despite a certain variation in the OHS provided in Swiss HEIs, most HEIs offer services for mental health protection. However, these services vary in terms of format and content, and especially in terms of financial access to them. The sources of this heterogeneity deserve a further investigation, as it might depend on regional (cantonal) differences in HEI funding and management, HEI size, type and scientific domain, and other factors. The role of health insurance can be also determinant. Despite its compulsory subscription by all Swiss residents, no public health insurance exists in Switzerland but rather a plenty of private insurance companies with very different prices, policies and conditions. This aspect should be investigated more in depth, as it may determine the access to the appropriate service when it is necessary in a researcher's career.

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